

IWSSPA

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP ON SOUND
SIGNAL PROCESSING APPLICATIONS 2025

Rota, Spain
July 2025

INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP ON SOUND SIGNAL PROCESSING APPLICATIONS 2025
BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Editors

Antonio J. Muñoz-Montoro, Universidad de Jaén

Mirco Pezzoli, Politecnico di Milano

Julio J. Carabias-Orti, Universidad de Jaén

José Ranilla, Universidad de Oviedo

Pedro Vera-Candeas, Universidad de Jaén

Citation Recommendation

Muñoz-Montoro, Antonio J.; Pezzoli, Mirco; Carabias-Orti, Julio J.; Ranilla, José; Vera-Candeas, Pedro (eds.). International Workshop on Sound Signal Processing Applications 2025: Book of Abstracts. DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16790182

License

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

Sponsors

Welcoming Note

General Co-Chair

Dr. Antonio J. Muñoz-Montoro
Universidad de Jaén, Spain

On behalf of the IWSSPA 2025 Organizing Committee, it is both an honor and a pleasure to welcome you to this new edition of the International Workshop on Sound Signal Processing Applications, once again held as a satellite event of CMMSE. This event serves as the meeting point for researchers, engineers and practitioners from across the globe who share a common passion for advancing the frontiers of sound signal processing.

This workshop is conceived as a space for

meaningful scientific dialogue, where novel ideas, rigorous methodologies and innovative applications can be shared and debated. The rapid evolution of our field, driven by advances in machine learning, sensor technology and computational acoustics, makes gatherings such as IWSSPA particularly valuable for fostering collaboration and sparking new research directions.

We extend our deepest appreciation to the authors, whose contributions form the backbone of this event. Each presentation reflects a substantial investment of time, creativity and scientific rigor, and we are confident that the diversity and quality of the works presented will inspire fruitful discussions.

Our gratitude also goes to the institutions and sponsors whose continued support makes this event possible. Their commitment not only sustains the scientific exchange but also enables us to create an environment where both professional and personal connections can flourish.

Finally, we acknowledge the tireless work of the organizing team and local coordinators, whose attention to detail and dedication to excellence ensure that IWSSPA 2025 runs smoothly. From logistical arrangements to participant engagement, their efforts are essential to the success of this workshop.

Conference Programme

TUESDAY, JULY 8

09:30 – 10:30 Registration

Plenary talk

16:00 – 17:00 *Prof. Christian Constanda - University of Tulsa (USA)*

Generalized Fourier series method for an elastic plate with a multiply connected middle plane domain

WEDNESDAY, JULY 9

Plenary talk

16:00 – 17:00 *Prof. Kunquan Lan - Toronto Metropolitan University (Canada)*

Recent advances in equivalences of linear or nonlinear fractional differential equations with integral equations

17:00 – 18:00 **CMMSE POSTER SESSION**

At room 2

FRIDAY, JULY 11

Regular session

Chairman: *Prof. Pedro Vera-Candeas*

Session time: 9:00 – 12:00

Location: Room 1

9:00 – 9:20 **ARVEDI HOA-RIRS: MEASURING THE SPATIAL ACOUSTICS OF A HISTORIC VIOLIN CONCERT HALL**

Mirco Pezzoli, Politecnico di Milano

9:20 – 9:40 **DEEP LEARNING-DRIVEN OBJECT TRACKING FOR ENHANCED ACOUSTIC BEAMFORMING IN DYNAMIC ENVIRONMENTS**

Jose Antonio Belloch Rodriguez, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid

9:40 – 10:00 **INCREMENTAL SEMI-SUPERVISED DOMAIN ADAPTATION FROM SYNTHETIC TO REAL AUDIO FOR IN-VEHICLE SOUND EVENT DETECTION**

Máximo Cobos, Universitat de València

10:00 – 10:20 **BLEEDING MATRICES: A NEW TOOL FOR MUSIC SOURCE SEPARATION ANALYSIS AND EVALUATION**

David Diaz-Guerra, Tampere University

10:20 – 10:40 **MULTICHANNEL ACTIVE NOISE EQUALIZATION OF NARROWBAND NOISE USING REMOTE MICROPHONE TECHNIQUES**

Alberto González Salvador, Universitat Politècnica de València

10:40 – 11:00 **PERCEPTUALLY-MOTIVATED LOSS FUNCTIONS FOR MULTICHANNEL AUDIO DEBLEEDING: A COMPARATIVE STUDY IN ORCHESTRAL RECORDINGS**

Pedro Vera Candeas, Universidad de Jaén

Coffee break

11:20 – 11:40 **SEMICOPRIME MICROPHONE ARRAYS FOR SURVEILLANCE APPLICATIONS**

Manuel Rosa-Zurera, Universidad de Alcalá

11:40 – 12:00 **LEARNING TOOLS FOR FILTER DESIGN IN SOUND FIELD APPLICATIONS**

Alberto González Salvador, Universitat Politècnica de València

12:00 – 12:20 **DESIGN AND DEMONSTRATION OF A LOW-COST AUDITORY EVOKED POTENTIAL RECORDING SYSTEM BASED ON CONSUMER ELECTRONICS: APPLICATION FOR DISSEMINATING AUDIOLOGICAL CONCEPTS IN SCHOOLS AND SCIENCE MUSEUMS**

Ángel de la Torre, Universidad de Granada

Table of Contents

Arvedi HOA-RIRs: Measuring the Spatial Acoustics of a Historic Violin Concert Hall <i>Federico Miotello, Paolo Ostan, Mirco Pezzoli and Fabio Antonacci</i>	1
Deep Learning-driven Object Tracking for Enhanced Acoustic Beamforming in Dynamic Environments <i>Jorge Ortigoso-Narro, Jose A. Belloch and Maximo Cobos</i>	5
Incremental Semi-supervised Domain Adaptation from Synthetic to Real Audio for In-vehicle Sound Event Detection <i>Carlos Castorena, Maximo Cobos and Francesc J. Ferri</i>	7
Bleeding Matrices: A New Tool for Music Source Separation Analysis and Evaluation <i>Malakias Kosonen and David Diaz-Guerra</i>	10
Multichannel Active Noise Equalization of Narrowband Noise using Remote Microphone Techniques <i>Miguel Ferrer, Gloria Punzano, Maria de Diego and Alberto González</i>	13
Perceptually-motivated Loss Functions for Multichannel Audio Debleeding: A Comparative Study in Orchestral Recordings <i>Pablo Cabañas-Molero, Pablo Revuelta, Jaime García-Martínez, Raquel Cortina and Pedro Vera-Candeas</i>	16
Semicoprime Microphone Arrays for Surveillance Applications <i>Diana Tejera-Berengué, Gonzalo Corral-García, FangFang Zhu-Zhou, Manuel Rosa-Zurera, Manuel Utrilla-Manso and Roberto Gil-Pita</i>	18
Learning Tools for Filter Design in Sound Field Applications <i>Miguel Ferrer, Maria de Diego, Juan Garcia and Alberto González</i>	21
Design and Demonstration of a Low-cost Auditory Evoked Potential Recording System Based on Consumer Electronics: Application for Disseminating Audio-logical Concepts in Schools and Science Museums <i>Angel de la Torre, Isaac M. Alvarez, Maria Raya, Juan A. Muñoz-Orellana, Juan Martín-Lagos and Juan A. Torres-Lara</i>	24

Abstracts

*Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop
on Sound Signal Processing Applications, IWSSPA 2025
July 8–11, 2025.*

Arvedi HOA-RIRs: Measuring the Spatial Acoustics of a Historic Violin Concert Hall

Federico Miotello, Paolo Ostan, Mirco Pezzoli and Fabio Antonacci

*Dipartimento di Elettronica, Informazione e Bioingegneria, Politecnico di Milano, Milan,
Italy*

emails: {federico.miotello}, {paolo.ostan}, {mirco.pezzoli},
{fabio.antonacci}@polimi.it

Abstract

We present a novel dataset of Higher-Order Ambisonics (HOA) Room Impulse Responses (RIRs) captured in the Giovanni Arvedi Auditorium, a concert hall within the *Violin Museum* in Cremona, Italy. The dataset was acquired using multiple Voyage Audio Spatial Mic Dante arrays, each capable of capturing the sound field up to 2nd-order Ambisonics. Measurements were performed using five sources positioned on the stage in a string quartet layout. This dataset is intended for research in spatial audio rendering, virtual acoustics, sound field reconstruction, and perceptual evaluation. It provides a rare example of high-order RIRs measured in a musically and historically significant environment. *Key words: room impulse response, ambisonics microphone, spatial audio*

Extended abstract

1 Proposal

In recent years, the interest in spatial audio technologies has significantly grown, driven by applications in augmented and virtual reality, immersive music experiences, and advanced acoustic simulations. Techniques such as binaural rendering, and sound field synthesis [1, 2] increasingly rely on precise modeling of real acoustic environments and benefit from the availability of multichannel and spatially-aware Room Impulse Response (RIR) datasets.

Among the available RIR datasets, many focus on telecommunication contexts [3, 4, 5] or controlled laboratory settings [6, 7]. However, fewer resources exist that provide high-order spatial data measured in real-world acoustic spaces specifically designed for musical performance. In particular, reverberant environments optimized for classical music are underrepresented, despite their relevance for applications like virtual acoustic rendering of instrumental performances or realistic auralizations for cultural heritage preservation.

In this paper, we present a novel dataset of Higher-Order RIRs captured in the Giovanni Arvedi Auditorium located within the *Violin Museum* in Cremona, Italy. This concert hall, seen in Fig. 1a is uniquely engineered to enhance the projection, clarity, and natural resonance of bowed string instruments, especially those in the renowned collection of historical

Figure 1: (a) View and (b) planimetry of the Giovanni Arvedi Auditorium.

violins (including several Stradivari) preserved in the museum. To capture the spatial characteristics of the hall, we employed the Voyage Audio Spatial Mic Dante. Each unit features 8 prepolarized condenser capsules arranged in a spherical geometry, enabling the capture of a sound field up to the 2nd order Ambisonics. Measurements were conducted using multiple loudspeaker and receiver positions to simulate various stage and audience configurations. The resulting dataset includes 8-channel RIRs, as well as corresponding metadata detailing array geometry, source–receiver distances, and environmental parameters.

2 Results and Discussion

Measurements were conducted across a wide area of the hall, including two audience seating sections (highlighted in blue and orange in Fig. 1b) and the stage area (shown in gray in Fig. 1b). The auditorium accommodates 475 seats and exhibits a reverberation time of approximately 1.5s when unoccupied and 1.4s when occupied. It measures approximately 36 m in length, 14 m in width, and 14 m in height. The building materials include a painted plaster ceiling, plaster and wood walls, historic doors, a wooden audience floor, and a stage floor made of Alaskan Yellow Cedar. All RIRs were recorded using logarithmic sine sweeps ranging from 50 Hz to 22 kHz, each lasting 10 s, and sampled at 48 kHz.

In the seating areas, the microphones were positioned at a height of approximately 1.25 m correspondingly to the typical head height of a seated listener. The two sampled seating sections consist of 64 and 65 seats, respectively. The stage area, was also densely sampled, measuring RIRs in a fine rectangular grid. During all acquisitions, 5 sources placed on the stage, which can be seen in Fig. 1a, were considered. The source positions are approximately indicated in Fig. 1b. Four Genelec 8020D loudspeakers were arranged in a trapezoidal configuration to simulate a string quartet, while a fifth omnidirectional source, a B&K OmniPower Sound Source was placed at the center of the stage. In total, the dataset comprises approximately 260 distinct microphone positions across the entire measurement area. Considering the 5 sources, the dataset includes more than 1300 HOM RIRs. We provide acoustically precise spatial positioning data, which is particularly relevant for many potential applications, including rendering, simulation, and perceptual evaluation.

FIRST AUTHOR ET AL.

Acknowledgments

This work has been funded by “REPERTORIUM project. Grant agreement number 101095065. Horizon Europe. Cluster II. Culture, Creativity and Inclusive Society. Call HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01-02” and by the European Union (EU) under the NextGenerationEU partnership on “Telecommunications of the Future” (PE00000001 - program “RESTART”).

References

- [1] F. Zotter and M. Frank, *Ambisonics: A practical 3D audio theory for recording, studio production, sound reinforcement, and virtual reality*. Springer Nature, 2019.
- [2] X. Karakonstantis and E. Fernandez-Grande, “Generative adversarial networks with physical sound field priors,” *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 154, no. 2, pp. 1226–1238, 2023.
- [3] T. Dietzen, R. Ali, M. Taseska, and T. van Waterschoot, “Myriad: a multi-array room acoustic database,” *EURASIP Journal on Audio, Speech, and Music Processing*, vol. 2023, no. 1, pp. 1–14, 2023.
- [4] E. Hadad, F. Heese, P. Vary, and S. Gannot, “Multichannel audio database in various acoustic environments,” in *2014 14th International Workshop on Acoustic Signal Enhancement (IWAENC)*. IEEE, 2014, pp. 313–317.
- [5] F. Miotello, P. Ostan, M. Pezzoli, L. Comanducci, A. Bernardini, F. Antonacci, and A. Sarti, “Homula-rir: A room impulse response dataset for teleconferencing and spatial audio applications acquired through higher-order microphones and uniform linear microphone arrays,” in *2024 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing Workshops (ICASSPW)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 795–799.
- [6] J.-W. Choi and F. Zotter, “Six degrees-of-freedom room impulse response dataset measured over a dense loudspeaker grid (6drir-dl),” in *Audio Engineering Society Conference: AES 2023 International Conference on Spatial and Immersive Audio*. Audio Engineering Society, 2023.
- [7] G. Götz, S. J. Schlecht, and V. Pulkki, “A dataset of higher-order ambisonic room impulse responses and 3d models measured in a room with varying furniture,” in *2021 Immersive and 3D Audio: from Architecture to Automotive (I3DA)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–8.

©IWSSPA

*Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop
on Sound Signal Processing Applications, IWSSPA 2025
July 8–11, 2025.*

Deep Learning-Driven Object Tracking for Enhanced Acoustic Beamforming in Dynamic Environments

Jorge Ortigoso-Narro¹, Jose A. Belloch¹ and Maximo Cobos²

¹ *Dpto. de Tecnología Electrónica, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Madrid, Spain*

² *Departamento de Informática, Universitat de València, Spain*

emails: jortigoso@ing.uc3m.es, jbelloc@ing.uc3m.es, maximo.cobos@uv.es

Abstract

This work presents a compact embedded system that integrates deep learning-based 3D object tracking with acoustic beamforming using a MEMS-based concentric circular microphone array. Designed for dynamic environments such as teleconferencing and assistive devices, the system fuses visual perception and spatial audio processing to improve sound source localization and separation in real time.

The system combines three key components:

1. A visual module based on stereo or monocular depth cameras,
2. A planar MEMS microphone array with 2D steering capabilities (azimuth and elevation),
3. An NVIDIA Jetson Orin Nano processor managing the visual-audio pipeline.

Object tracking is performed using a lightweight YOLOv10n network [1], optimized for real-time operation, which estimates the 3D coordinates of persons or sound sources. This positional data is used to calculate steering vectors that guide delay-and-sum beamforming on the MEMS array. Both monocular and stereo-based depth estimation models were evaluated, with filtered SGBM selected for robustness in acoustically challenging environments.

Experiments in anechoic chambers involved static and dynamic scenarios, including dual-source setups with moving targets. Results demonstrate clear signal-to-interference ratio (SIR) improvements when using beamforming guided by visual tracking, both in tone-based and speech-based experiments. Performance was quantified across multiple frames using SIR metrics and azimuth angle estimations, confirming the system's ability to isolate target audio sources even as they move.

DEEP LEARNING-DRIVEN OBJECT TRACKING FOR ENHANCED ACOUSTIC BEAMFORMING

These findings highlight the potential of combining deep neural visual tracking with MEMS beamforming for low-power, real-time directional audio capture in embedded applications.

Key words: Beamforming, Deep Learning, MEMS Arrays, Depth Estimation, Embedded Systems

References

- [1] A. Wang, H. Chen, L. Liu, K. Chen, Z. Lin, J. Han, and G. Ding, "YOLOv10: Real-time end-to-end object detection," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2405.14458*, 2024.

*Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop
on Sound Signal Processing Applications, IWSSPA 2025
July 8–11, 2025.*

Incremental Semi-supervised Domain Adaptation from Synthetic to Real Audio for In-Vehicle Sound Event Detection

Carlos Castorena¹, Maximo Cobos¹ and Francesc J. Ferri¹

¹ *Dpto. de Informàtica, Universitat de València, Burjassot, Spain*

emails: carlos.castorena@uv.es, maximo.cobos@uv.es, francesc.ferri@uv.es

Abstract

Sound event detection (SED) in driving environments is crucial for in-cabin monitoring and intelligent vehicle systems. However, models trained on synthetic driving audio often suffer from significant performance degradation when applied to real-world in-car recordings due to domain mismatches caused by cabin acoustics, background noise, and microphone variability. In this work, we extend a recently proposed semi-supervised incremental adaptation framework, originally developed for speech emotion recognition, to the SED domain. Our method employs a modified k-means algorithm to iteratively select representative samples from the target (real) domain in a latent space, allowing the model to gradually adapt using a minimal set of manually labeled data. Experiments involve training on synthetic soundscapes and adapting to real audio captured inside a vehicle cabin. Results show that the proposed method consistently outperforms random selection and achieves comparable performance to more label-intensive techniques, effectively bridging the synthetic-to-real gap. This approach offers a practical solution for domain adaptation in data-scarce SED scenarios and demonstrates strong potential for real-world deployment in intelligent transportation systems.

Key words: Sound event detection, Domain adaptation, Semi-supervised learning

Extended abstract

1 Proposal and Methodology

Sound event detection (SED) systems are increasingly relevant for advanced driver assistance and in-cabin monitoring [1]. However, the performance of models trained exclusively on synthetic audio, which is often used to generate large-scale and diverse training data,

CASTORENA ET AL.

degrades when deployed on real in-car recordings. This performance gap mostly arises from domain mismatches caused by microphone characteristics, cabin acoustics, environmental noise, and reverberation [2].

We propose a semi-supervised domain adaptation method that incrementally refines a synthetic-domain SED model using a small number of labeled examples from the target domain. The method extends our previous work on speech emotion recognition (SER), which uses a modified k-means algorithm to iteratively select representative samples in a learned latent space [3]. In each iteration, samples from both source (synthetic) and target (real) domains are selected and used to retrain the model, improving alignment between domains. The base model employs a pretrained convolutional or transformer-based embedding extractor (e.g., PANNs [4] or AST [5]), followed by a domain adapter and classifier. The latent space is regularized using a center loss to enforce class separation. The proposed incremental strategy enables efficient adaptation while minimizing labeling effort.

2 Results and Discussion

Experiments were conducted using synthetic driving datasets generated from publicly available sound event libraries and real audio recordings captured inside a mid-sized vehicle. We evaluated performance using both frame and event-based metrics on a set of common in-vehicle sounds (e.g. sirens, horns, etc.). The proposed method was compared against random sample selection and an optimistic-bound using Protodash [6], a state-of-the-art prototype selection algorithm. Across five iterations with 5 labeled samples per iteration, our incremental strategy consistently outperformed the random baseline and achieved competitive results relative to Protodash, while requiring fewer labeled examples. Visualizations of the latent space show progressive alignment between synthetic and real data clusters. The model also exhibited improved robustness to ambient variations and background noise. These findings confirm that the proposed adaptation strategy is well-suited for real-world deployment in vehicles, offering a practical trade-off between performance and annotation cost.

Acknowledgments

Authors would like to thank the Spanish Research Agency (AEI) and the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) for partially funding this research within the projects with references TED2021-131003B-C21 and PID2022-137048OB-C41 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by the “EU Union NextGenerationEU/PRTR”. We also thank *Generalitat Valenciana*, the *Santiago Grisolia* program for financing this work (GRISOLIAP/2021/060, CPI-21-232).

©IWSSPA

References

- [1] C. Castorena, M. Cobos, J. Lopez-Ballester, and F. J. Ferri, “A Safety-Oriented Framework for Sound Event Detection in Driving Scenarios,” *Applied Acoustics*, vol. 215, p. 109719, 2024.
- [2] A. Mesaros, T. Heittola, and T. Virtanen, “Acoustic Scene Classification in DCASE 2019 Challenge: Closed and Open Set Classification and Data Mismatch Setups,” *Detection and Classification of Acoustic Scenes and Events 2019*, New York, NY, USA, 2019.
- [3] C. Castorena, M. Cobos, and F. J. Ferri, “An Incremental Selection Method for Semi-supervised Speaker Adaptation in Speech Emotion Recognition,” (*submitted*), May 2025.
- [4] Q. Kong, Y. Cao, T. Iqbal, Y. Wang, W. Wang, and M. D. Plumbley, “PANNs: Large-Scale Pretrained Audio Neural Networks for Audio Pattern Recognition,” *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, vol. 28, pp. 2880–2894, 2020.
- [5] Y. Gong, Y.-A. Chung, and J. R. Glass, “AST: Audio Spectrogram Transformer,” in *Proc. Interspeech*, 2021, pp. 571–575.
- [6] K. S. Gurumoorthy, A. Dhurandhar, G. Cecchi, and C. Aggarwal, “Efficient Data Representation by Selecting Prototypes with Importance Weights,” in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. on Data Mining (ICDM)*, 2019, pp. 260–269.
- [7] A. Mesaros, T. Heittola, and T. Virtanen, “Acoustic Scene Classification in DCASE 2019 Challenge: Closed and Open Set Classification and Data Mismatch Setups,” *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, vol. 28, pp. 879–892, 2020.

*Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop
on Sound Signal Processing Applications, IWSSPA 2025
July 8–11, 2025.*

Bleeding Matrices: A New Tool for Music Source Separation Analysis and Evaluation

Malakias Kosonen and David Diaz-Guerra¹

¹ *Audio Research Group, Tampere University, Finland*
emails: david.diaz-guerra@tuni.fi

Abstract

Signal-to-distortion, signal-to-interference, and signal-to-artifacts ratios are the most common objective metrics for evaluating music source separation systems. The signal-to-interference ratio measures how much of the error in a separated stem comes from other sources not having been completely removed, but does not provide information about which sources are those. Inspired by the confusion matrices used to analyze and evaluate classification systems, we propose the use of bleeding matrices to visualize how much of the interference in every separated stem comes from every interferent source.

Key words: Music source separation, sound source separation, signal-to-distortion ratio, signal-to-interference ratio

Extended abstract

1 Proposal and Methodology

In recent years, the state of the art of music source separation has been revolutionized thanks to the use of deep learning models [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6]. Different models have been published that achieve really good results in separating drums, bass, voice, and “others” on the MUSDB18 dataset [7]. However, the evaluation of these models remains challenging.

Signal-to-distortion, signal-to-interference, and signal-to-artifacts ratios (SDR, SIR, and SAR, respectively) are the most common objective metrics for evaluating music source separation systems [8]. SDR measures the differences between the separation estimates and their ground truths, regardless of the origin of those differences, while SIR focuses on the differences that correspond to other sources not having been completely removed (also known as interferences or bleeding) and SAR focuses on differences that cannot be explained by the input signal, so they are artifacts generated by the separation system.

Figure 1: Bleeding matrices for the pretrained X-UMX, X-UMXL, and HT-Demucs models. Every cell represents the SIR for every target-interference pair in decibels.

In this work, we propose computing independently the contribution of every interference source to the SIR and, inspired by the confusion matrices used to analyze classification systems, visualize the results in what we call bleeding matrices. We follow the same projectors defined in [8] and implemented in [9] to compute the energy of the interferences by finding the finite impulse response (FIR) filter that best approximates every interference source to the estimate, but compute their energy separately so we can compute a different logarithmic ratio for every one of them. This processing is done in 1-second segments, and then the results of every track are aggregated by computing the median value of its frames and the dataset result is aggregated by computing the median value of every track.

2 Results and Discussion

To showcase the interest of our proposed bleeding matrices, we computed them for the pretrained versions of 3 state-of-the-art models: X-UMX [3], X-UMXL [6], and HT-Demucs [5]. The results, represented in Fig. 1, allow us to observe some characteristics of the separation models that were hidden in the original SIR. For example, we can see how all the models are very good at removing the bass signal from the vocals stem, but they have problems removing the “others” class from the bass stem. We can also see how HT-Demucs, the most powerful of the evaluated models, clearly outperforms X-UMX and X-UMXL in removing the bass signal from the drums stem.

We believe that the bleeding matrices are an interesting tool for analyzing the performance of separation models further than the classic SDR, SIR, and SAR metrics and hope that they can guide the development of better models in the future. We have published our modified version of [9] to compute the bleeding matrices on GitHub: <https://github.com/MalakiasK/sigsep-mus-eval-ssir>

M. KOSONEN ET AL.

Acknowledgments

This work has been partially funded by “REPERTORIUM” project. Grant agreement number 101095065. Horizon Europe. Cluster II. Culture, Creativity and Inclusive Society. Call HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01-02.”

References

- [1] Défossez, A., Usunier, N., Bottou, L., and Bach, F. (2019). Music source separation in the waveform domain. arXiv preprint arXiv:1911.13254.
- [2] Hennequin, R., Khlif, A., Voituret, F., and Moussallam, M. (2020). Spleeter: a fast and efficient music source separation tool with pre-trained models. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 5(50), 2154.
- [3] Sawata, R., Uhlich, S., Takahashi, S., and Mitsufuji, Y. (2021, June). All for one and one for all: Improving music separation by bridging networks. In *ICASSP 2021-2021 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)* (pp. 51-55). IEEE.
- [4] Luo, Y., and Yu, J. (2023). Music source separation with band-split RNN. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing*, 31, 1893-1901.
- [5] Rouard, S., Massa, F., and Défossez, A. (2023, June). Hybrid transformers for music source separation. In *ICASSP 2023-2023 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)* (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- [6] Sawata, R., Takahashi, N., Uhlich, S., Takahashi, S., and Mitsufuji, Y. (2024). The whole is greater than the sum of its parts: improving music source separation by bridging networks. *EURASIP Journal on Audio, Speech, and Music Processing*, 2024(1), 39.
- [7] Rafi, Z., Liutkus, A., Stöter, F.-R., Mimilakis, S. I., and Bittner, R. (2019). MUSDB18-HQ - an uncompressed version of MUSDB18 (1.0.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3338373>
- [8] Vincent, E., Gribonval, R., and Févotte, C. (2006). Performance measurement in blind audio source separation. *IEEE transactions on audio, speech, and language processing*, 14(4), 1462-1469.
- [9] Stöter, F.R., et al. (2021). sigsep/sigsep-mus-eval: museval 0.4.0 (v0.4.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4486535ain>.

©IWSSPA

*Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop
on Sound Signal Processing Applications, IWSSPA 2025
July 8–11, 2025.*

Multichannel Active Noise Equalization of Narrowband Noise Using Remote Microphone Techniques

Miguel Ferrer, Gloria Punzano, Maria de Diego, Alberto Gonzalez

*Institute of Telecommunications and Multimedia Applications, Universitat Politècnica de
València, Valencia, Spain*

emails: mferrer@dcom.upv.es, mdediego@dcom.upv.es, agonzal@dcom.upv.es

Abstract

This paper introduces a novel multichannel active noise equalization (ANE) method designed for the effective control of multitonal narrowband noise using a virtual sensing technique. The proposed methodology enables independent adjustment of the attenuation levels for each tonal component at multiple spatially distributed control points. In addition, the algorithm employs a virtual remote microphone approach, which extends control capabilities to spatial locations where no physical sensors are present. This approach offers a practical and efficient solution for multichannel narrowband noise control in scenarios where deploying sensors at all desired control points is limited or unfeasible. The proposed ANE system demonstrates good performance in real-time acoustic environments and is suitable for a wide range of applications, including industrial and automotive.

Key words: Active noise control, noise equalization, virtual control

Extended abstract

1 Proposal

Narrowband active noise equalization was introduced by Kuo [1] as a method for controlling the residual levels of tonal noise components. The main advantage of this approach lies in its low implementation cost, as the filtering process can be performed in either an in-phase/quadrature or magnitude/phase configuration, requiring only two real coefficients per filter. This allows for the use of a fast filtered-x LMS algorithm for tonal noise control.

Unlike conventional methods, this algorithm updates the control filter coefficients by minimizing an auxiliary signal, referred to as the pseudo-error, rather than the actual residual error measured at the sensor, which remains equalized.

The single-channel ANE algorithm can be described by the following equation to equalize a tonal noise of frequency f_0 , being $e(n)$ the error signal at the control point and $S(f_0)$ the complex coefficient of the frequency response of the secondary path between the controlling loudspeaker and the error sensor:

$$w(n+1) = w(n) + e(n)|S(f_0)|\cos(2\pi f_0 n + \angle S(f_0))$$

$$\tilde{w}(n+1) = \tilde{w}(n) + e(n)|S(f_0)|\sin(2\pi f_0 n + \angle S(f_0))$$

This algorithm can be extended to multichannel systems to control multiple tonal components, enabling the design of specific spectral profiles across different frequencies [2, 3]. Two equalization strategies are considered: the multiple pseudo-error signal approach and the common pseudo-error signal approach. Both methods yield comparable performance, differing mainly in how the pseudo-error signal used for filter adaptation is computed. Furthermore, performance can be further improved by assigning a different equalization profile to each control point within the system [4].

In this work, the Virtual Multichannel Active Noise Equalizer (VM-ANE) is proposed, extending the previous approach by incorporating remote microphone techniques, as in [5]. This capability enables control at locations different from those where the physical microphones are placed, introducing a highly practical functionality for real-time applications. To achieve this, transfer functions (also referred to as observation functions) must be computed to estimate the tonal noise at the virtual control points based on measurements from the physical (monitoring) microphones. This estimate relies on prior knowledge of the acoustic paths involved.

2 Conclusions

The VM-ANE method offers an efficient approach to equalizing narrowband noise with multiple tonal components, using local oscillators tuned to each frequency. It enables virtual control at locations without physical sensors and allows independent equalization of each tone at all control or virtual points. The method only requires the frequency responses between loudspeakers and control or virtual locations at the tonal frequencies. Observation functions for virtual control can be directly derived from these responses. To use this frequency-specific information, error signals must be decomposed into their tonal components. Notably, the proposed method achieves results comparable to those of an equivalent system with physical control at the virtualized points.

FIRST AUTHOR ET AL.

Acknowledgments

This work has been funded by the GVA under Grant CIPROM/2022/20; by the MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and European Union NextGenerationEU/PRTR (PDC2022-133651-C21); by MICIN under Grant PID2021-125736OB-I00 (MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/, “ERDF A way of making Europe”), and by the EU through IN-NOVA, active reduction of noise transmitted into and from enclosures through encapsulated structures (HORIZON-MSCA-2021-DN, Marie Skłodowska-Curie under Grant 101073037).

References

- [1] S. M. Kuo, Xuan Kong, Shaojie Chen and Wenge Hao, “Analysis and design of narrow-band active noise control systems,” Proceedings of the 1998 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing, ICASSP ’98 (Cat. No.98CH36181), Seattle, WA, USA, 1998, pp. 3557-3560 vol.6, doi: 10.1109/ICASSP.1998.679642.
- [2] M. de Diego, A. Gonzalez, M. Ferrer, and G. Piñero, “Multichannel active noise control system for local spectral reshaping of multifrequency noise,” J. Sound Vib., vol. 274, no. 1, pp. 249–271, 2004.
- [3] A. Gonzalez, M. de Diego, M. Ferrer, and G. Piñero, “Multichannel active noise equalization of interior noise,” IEEE Trans. Audio, Speech, Lang. Process., vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 110–122, Jan. 2006
- [4] M. Ferrer, M. de Diego, A. Hassani, M. Moonen, G. Piñero and A. Gonzalez, “Multi-Tone Active Noise Equalizer With Spatially Distributed User-Selected Profiles,” in IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing, vol. 30, pp. 3199-3213, 2022
- [5] C. Antoñanzas, M. Ferrer, M. de Diego and A. Gonzalez, “Remote Microphone Technique for Active Noise Control Over Distributed Networks,” in IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing, vol. 31, pp. 1522-1535, 2023

*Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop
on Sound Signal Processing Applications
IWSSPA 2025, July 8 – July 11, 2025.*

Perceptually-Motivated Loss Functions for Multichannel Audio Debleeding: A Comparative Study in Orchestral Recordings

P. Cabañas-Molero¹, P. Revuelta², J. García-Martínez¹, R. Cortina² and P. Vera-Candeas¹

¹ *Department of Telecommunication Engineering, University of Jaén, Linares, Spain*

² *Department of Computer Science, University of Oviedo, Gijón, Spain*

emails: pcabanas@ujaen.es, revueltapablo@uniovi.es, jgm00115@red.ujaen.es,
cortina@uniovi.es, pvera@ujaen.es

Abstract

This work presents a comparative evaluation of perceptually motivated loss functions applied to the task of multichannel audio debleeding within the context of orchestral recordings. The study is framed within the REPERTORIUM project, where close-microphone recordings of real orchestral performances captured at The Spheres studio were processed to suppress inter-channel interference. A deep learning model trained on the synthetic, multi-instrumental SynthSOD dataset [1] was used to estimate the dry signal of each instrument by attenuating the leakage from others recorded in the same room.

We explore the impact of three loss functions on the subjective and objective quality of the separated signals: standard L1 norm, the non-differentiable perceptual metric proposed by Schuller [2], and the psychoacoustically-informed function from Wright and Välimäki [3]. Results highlight the trade-off between perceptual improvement and training stability, showing that while perceptual losses can enhance perceived audio quality, their non-differentiability may hinder convergence and robustness during training. Objective evaluation based on Signal-to-Distortion Ratio (SDR) across different configurations supports the analysis. These findings contribute to the design of more perceptually aligned training strategies for real-world multichannel source separation.

Key words: loss functions, psychoacoustic masking threshold, audio debleeding

Extended abstract

1 Proposal and Methodology

This work investigates the impact of perceptually motivated loss functions in deep learning-based debleeding for multichannel audio recordings. In the context of the REPERTORIUM and PRISMA-AI projects, we aim to improve the subjective quality of close-mic orchestral recordings by suppressing leakage between instruments. Our proposal evaluates whether psychoacoustic loss functions can enhance the perceptual separation without compromising training stability.

We use real multichannel orchestral recordings captured at The Spheres studio and apply a source separation model trained on the synthetic SynthSOD dataset, which includes simulated room conditions for various instruments. The model estimates the dry signal from each close mic while reducing interference from other sources. Three loss functions are compared:

- L1 norm
- [2] Perceptual loss (non-differentiable)
- [3] Psychoacoustic loss based on auditory masking

Training stability and perceptual effectiveness are assessed, with objective evaluation based on Signal-to-Distortion Ratio (SDR).

2 Results and Discussion

Our experiments show that perceptual losses can enhance the subjective quality of separated signals, but training instabilities arise when using non-differentiable metrics like [2]. The [3] loss offers a balance between perceptual improvement and convergence reliability. While L1 provides consistent optimization, its perceptual results are suboptimal. The findings highlight the need to align loss function design with both auditory perception and computational feasibility for practical multichannel source separation.

Acknowledgments

This work has been funded by REPERTORIUM project. Grant agreement number 101095065. Horizon Europe. Cluster II. Culture, Creativity and Inclusive society. Call HORIZON-CL2-2022- HERITAGE-01-02.

References

- [1] J. Garcia, D. Diaz, A. Politis, T. Virtanen, J.J. Carabias, y P. Vera-Candeas. SynthSOD: Developing an Heterogeneous Dataset for Orchestra Music Source Separation. *IEEE Open Journal of Signal Processing* 6 (2025): 129-37.
- [2] G. Schuller. Perceptual Loss Function. Teaching AI to Hear Like We Do: Psychoacoustics in Machine Learning. Workshop on Teaching AI to Hear Like We Do: Psychoacoustics in Machine Learning at the October 2022 AES Convention in New York, 2022.
- [3] A. Wright and V. Valimaki, "Perceptual loss function for neural modeling of audio systems," ICASSP 2020, Barcelona, Spain, 2020, pp. 251-255.

*Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop
on Sound Signal Processing Applications, IWSSPA 2025
July 8–11, 2025.*

Semicoprime microphone arrays for surveillance applications

Diana Tejera-Berengué¹, Gonzalo Corral-García¹, FangFang Zhu-Zhou¹,
Manuel Rosa-Zurera¹, Manuel Utrilla-Manso¹ and Roberto Gil-Pita¹

¹ *Signal Theory and Communications, University of Alcalá, Alcalá de Henares (Madrid),
Spain*

emails: diana.tejera@uah.es, gonzalo.corral@uah.es, roberto.gil@uah.es,
manuel.rosa@uah.es, manuel.utrilla@uah.es, roberto.gil@uah.es

Abstract

Acoustic surveillance systems rely on microphone arrays with spatial filtering to detect and localize sound sources, with applications ranging from industrial monitoring to unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) threat detection. A key challenge arises when using broadband signals, as array performance varies across frequencies, often compromising beam sharpness and sidelobe suppression. To address this, co-prime microphone arrays (CMAs) offer an efficient solution by creating extended virtual apertures with fewer sensors, enabling high-resolution direction-of-arrival (DoA) estimation at reduced cost. This paper explores a variation of the classical CMA known as the semi-coprime array (SCA), which introduces a third subarray to mitigate grating lobes and enhance sidelobe attenuation. The SCA architecture achieves a favorable trade-off between resolution, array compactness, and robustness, making it well-suited for advanced acoustic sensing applications.

Key words: coprime array, semi-coprime array, DOA, acoustic surveillance

1 Proposal and Methodology

Acoustic surveillance systems use microphone arrays to capture signals generated by sources of interest, implementing some form of spatial filtering. The applications are very diverse, ranging from acoustic monitoring in industry for anomaly detection to the detection of threats such as drones or UAVs. In all cases, the microphone array must have a narrow main lobe pointing pattern, while also providing good attenuation of the side-lobes relative to the main lobe. When working with broadband sound signals, the array's response at the extreme frequencies within the band can vary significantly, making it difficult to meet the aforementioned requirements across very different frequencies.

A possible solution is to use more advanced array architectures, such as co-prime arrays [1]. Co-prime Microphone Arrays (CMAs) are sparse arrays constructed from two uniform linear subarrays, defined by two co-prime integers M and N . These arrays offer extended aperture and high degrees of freedom with fewer physical elements, making them good alternatives for acoustic direction-of-arrival (DoA) estimation and source localization. Coprime Microphone Arrays allow for efficient array design using principles from number theory and signal processing. By leveraging coprime spacing, these arrays provide extended aperture and increased resolution capabilities while minimizing the number of required sensors.

A variation of the classical coprime array architecture is introduced with the aim of achieving an efficient trade-off between angular resolution, physical compactness, and side-lobe reduction. It corresponds to the so-called semi-coprime array (SCA), an architecture proposed in [2] as an extension of the classical coprime design. The SCA introduces a third uniformly-spaced subarray in order to cancel the grating lobes generated by the undersampling of the other two subarrays, whose spacing factors are multiples of coprime integers. The output with the minimum power among the scanned responses of the three subarrays is selected, resulting in the suppression of grating lobes and the highest sidelobes, giving rise to a cleaner and more robust radiation pattern. An example of beampattern is depicted in Fig.

Figure 1: Beampattern of SCA with minimum processor ($M = 3$, $N = 4$, $P = 2$, $Q = 2$).

Acknowledgments

This work was funded by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation under Project PID2021-129043OB-I00 (funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/FEDER, EU)

TEJERA-BERENGUÉ, D. ET AL.

References

- [1] P.P. Vaidyanathan, and Prabhu Pal, “Sparse sensing with co-prime sampling and array processing”, *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 59, No. 2, pp. 573-586, 2011.
- [2] Kaushallya Adhikari, “Sparse Sensing with Semi-Coprime Arrays”, arXiv preprint arXiv:1806.08419, 2018.

*Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop
on Sound Signal Processing Applications, IWSSPA 2025
July 8–11, 2025.*

Learning Tools for Filter Design in Sound Field Applications

Miguel Ferrer, Maria de Diego, Juan Garcia, Alberto Gonzalez

*Institute of Telecommunications and Multimedia Applications, Universitat Politècnica de
València, Valencia, Spain*

emails: mferrer@dcom.upv.es, mdediego@dcom.upv.es, agonzal@dcom.upv.es

Abstract

Sound field control applications use actuators (typically loudspeakers) to generate appropriate audio signals that create a desired acoustic environment. Similarly, sound source separation aims to estimate the signal from a specific source within a mixture of sounds coming from different spatial locations. In both cases, the desired outputs result from filtering known reference signals or measurements. Thus, filter design is crucial to system performance and is typically formulated as an optimization problem, often solved iteratively using adaptive filtering techniques. This work proposes a machine learning-based approach to design these filters, where the problem is reformulated into a model that can be trained directly from data.

Key words: Sound control, data-driven techniques, convolutional networks.

Extended abstract

1 Proposal

Many sound field control applications, such as active noise control (ANC) [1], transaural sound reproduction, localized sound reproduction, and generalized crosstalk cancellation, require filter designs that, assuming linear behavior, can often be modeled as simple FIR filters. The output signals of these filters are further shaped by acoustic propagation paths, which can also be modeled using FIR filters. As a result, these applications can be described as a chain of convolutions applied to known or measured signals to generate desired outputs. This structure enables data-driven filter design [2, 3], as both reference and target signals are available. Similarly, sound source separation aims to isolate signals from spatially distinct sources using microphone arrays. Microphone arrays capture each signal as filtered by its corresponding acoustic paths. By suitably combining these signals with properly designed

FIR filters, one can estimate the signal from each source, provided the filters cancel the contributions from other sources. This is analogous to sound field control, with the difference that propagation (modeled by FIR filters) occurs before processing.

This work explores the use of simple neural network-based machine learning tools to compute the FIR filters needed for both sound field control and source separation [4]. Nevertheless, it is important to bear in mind that, in certain scenarios, such as those involving nonlinear effects, a more complex model may be needed, potentially involving nonlinear processing or IIR filters [6, 7].

For the ANC application we consider a system with I reference signals, J actuators, and K error sensors, requiring a total of IJ control filters. In this setup, the disturbance signals $d_k(n)$ represent the noise to be cancelled, and the objective is to minimize the error signals $e_k(n)$. The control filters \mathbf{w}_{ij} are optimized to minimize the mean squared error (MSE) of the error signals. The ANC system can be modeled using a neural network (NN) composed of linear 1D convolutional layers that estimate the optimal control filter coefficients. Acoustic propagation paths are implemented as fixed (non-trainable) FIR filters, while the control filters are defined as trainable parameters. The loss function is based on the MSE strategy available in the Keras toolbox. When the network successfully minimizes the loss, the trained convolutional weights correspond to filters that achieve effective noise cancellation.

A similar setup should be considered for transaural audio reproduction, where the goal is to obtain a delayed version of the target signal at the control points. As in ANC, the NN is trained using broadband signals as input, but in this case, the target outputs are delayed versions of the input signal $s(n)$ (with $I = 1$, $d_k(n) = 0$, and $e_k(n) = s(n - D_k)$ being D_k a delay that guarantees filter causality). Localized reproduction and generalized crosstalk cancellation share related objectives, aiming to achieve the desired signal at specific control points while minimizing interference.

The source separation task does not follow the same model as the previous applications, since acoustic propagation occurs before signal processing. In this case, the required setup can also be modeled using a NN composed of 1D convolutional layers. Specifically, the first layer includes fixed, non-trainable FIR filters that represent the acoustic propagation from source s to microphone m , while the trainable parameters correspond to the convolutional blocks \mathbf{w}_{my} that model the signal processing. The goal is to design M filters which, when applied to the M microphone signals, recover one of the S source signals.

Finally, it is worth noting that by employing a simple NN with a MSE-based loss function, it is possible to achieve performance comparable to traditional estimation methods such as optimal Wiener filtering or adaptive schemes, which in some cases can lead to significant computational savings. Moreover, while the proposed approaches do not explicitly address nonlinear filtering, such aspects can certainly be incorporated into future developments.

FIRST AUTHOR ET AL.

Acknowledgments

This work has been funded by the GVA under Grant CIPROM/2022/20; by the MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and European Union NextGenerationEU/PRTR (PDC2022-133651-C21); by MICIN under Grant PID2021-125736OB-I00 (MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/, “ERDF A way of making Europe”), and by the EU through IN-NOVA, active reduction of noise transmitted into and from enclosures through encapsulated structures (HORIZON-MSCA-2021-DN, Marie Skłodowska-Curie under Grant 101073037).

References

- [1] Sen M. Kuo and Dennis Morgan. Active Noise Control Systems: Algorithms and DSP Implementations (1st. ed.). John Wiley Sons, Inc., 1995, USA.
- [2] S.O. Haykin, Neural Networks and Learning Machines, 2008. Pearson Education, Upper Saddle River, NJ, Third edition, 2009.
- [3] M. Milanese, C. Novara, K. Hsu and K. Poolla, Filter design from data: direct vs. two-step approaches, 2006 American Control Conference, Minneapolis, MN, USA, 2006.
- [4] A. Cichoki, R. Unbehauen, Neural Networks for Optimization and Signal Processing. John Wiley Sons, third ed., 1994.
- [5] Shi D, Lam B, Ooi K, Shen X, Gan WS. Selective fixed-filter active noise control based on convolutional neural network, Signal Processing, 190:108317, (2022).
- [6] Cheng-Yuan Chang, Fang-Bor Luoh, Enhancement of active noise control using neural-based filtered-X algorithm, Journal of Sound and Vibration, 305 (1–2):348-356,2007.
- [7] Xander Pike, Jordan Cheer, Generalised performance of neural network controllers for feedforward active noise control of nonlinear systems, Acta Acust.

©IWSSPA

*Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop
on Sound Signal Processing Applications, IWSSPA 2025
July 8–11, 2025.*

Design and demonstration of a low-cost auditory evoked potential recording system based on consumer electronics: application for disseminating audiological concepts in schools and science museums

**Angel de la Torre¹, Isaac M. Alvarez¹, Maria Raya¹, Juan A.
Muñoz-Orellana², Juan Martín-Lagos³ and Juan A. Torres-Lara⁴**

¹ *Department of Signal Theory, Telematics and Communications, CITIC-UGR. University
of Granada, Granada, Spain.*

² *Knowledge Transfer Office, University of Granada, Granada, Spain.*

³ *Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Hospital Clínico Universitario San Cecilio,
Granada, Spain.*

⁴ *Parque de las Ciencias, Granada, Spain.*

emails: atv@ugr.es, isamaru@ugr.es, mariarayarod@correo.ugr.es, orellana@ugr.es,
juanmartinlagos@hotmail.com, juanantonio.torres@parqueciencias.com

Abstract

We describe a robust, flexible, low-cost and open AEP recording system appropriate for research, education and dissemination purposes, with an example of a workshop for dissemination of audiology concepts. This workshop is being held in spring 2025 at several schools and at Granada Science Park museum (Parque de las Ciencias).

Key words: power line interference (PLI), biopotential recording system, auditory evoked potentials (AEP)

Extended abstract

1 Proposal and Methodology

Recording auditory evoked potentials involves technological difficulties due to the small amplitude and the presence of noise in the recording signal. One of the main limitations

is the power line interference (PLI). Techniques to reduce this interference usually involve complicated electronic designs and/or the need to record in a shielded room, which makes response acquisition difficult and expensive. In our multidisciplinary group we have developed a numerical procedure based on the cancellation of the frequency drift of the PLI, without the need for specific hardware. Thanks to this, it is possible to record high-quality biopotentials using low-cost consumer electronics components.

We have developed and evaluated an auditory evoked potential recording system using an audio preamplifier, an audio interface, a computer, and conventional wiring (components available at audio supply stores). This system is suitable for research, but also, due to its low cost, is suitable for educational and scientific dissemination activities aimed at audiences of different ages and educational levels. Based on this system, we have designed a workshop with the participation of volunteers to introduce basic concepts of audiology and auditory evoked potentials. This workshop is being held in spring 2025 in several schools and institutes and at the Science Park in Granada. The workshop includes recording and analysis of cardiac biopotentials (as an easy-to-acquire and describe signal) and the recording and analysis of auditory evoked potentials, to explain the neurological activity of the different stations of the auditory pathway from the brainstem to the primary cortical areas.

2 Results and Discussion

The recording system has been calibrated and validated by recording auditory evoked potentials from five subjects. The evoked responses have been compared with those obtained with a conventional recording system, validating the proposed architecture for recording evoked potentials. A workshop on cardiac biopotentials and auditory evoked potentials has been conducted using this system. At the time of submitting this abstract, three sessions of the workshop have been held, attended by students from five secondary school groups. The workshop is scheduled to be held in several primary & secondary schools and institutes and at the Granada Science Park throughout May/June/July 2025. The presentation of this work at the IWSSPA2025 conference will describe the acquisition system, the recordings obtained for validation, its use in the workshops, and may include a demonstration of its operation.

The proposed low-cost and robust to noise recording system offers great configuration flexibility, allowing its use for research with open-ended experimental designs. Furthermore, its low cost makes it suitable for educational and dissemination activities, as demonstrated by the workshops conducted. This experience opens a very interesting opportunity for bringing experimental audiology closer to educational environment and to society in general.

ÁNGEL DE LA TORRE ET AL.

Acknowledgments

The authors gratefully acknowledge all the volunteers who participated in the ECG and AEP recording sessions. This work was supported by the Spanish Government - Ministry of Science and Innovation [Project “Speech-AEPs”, grant number: PID2020-119073GB-I00] and by Junta de Andalucía - Consejería de Universidad, Investigación e Innovación [Project “Early-HHL-D”, grant number: P21.00152].

References

- [1] Hall, J.W., 2007. New handbook of auditory evoked potentials. Pearson Education, Boston. pp. 58–108.
- [2] de la Torre, A., Alvarez, I.M., Muñoz-Orellana, J.A., 2024a. An improved procedure for reduction of quasi-periodic interferences. European Application EP25166854.7, ESP202430935 (under evaluation, filing date 12-Nov-2024).
- [3] de la Torre, A., Sanchez, I., Alvarez, I.M., Segura, J.C., Valderrama, J.T., Muller, N., Vargas, J.L., 2024c. Multi-response deconvolution of auditory evoked potentials in a reduced representation space. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* 155, 3639–3653. doi:10.1121/10.0026228.
- [4] de la Torre, A., Valderrama, J.T., Alvarez, I.M., Segura, J.C., Vargas, J.L., Palma, A.J., Carvajal, M.A., Pusibet, A., 2023. Live demonstration of a portable, affordable, and versatile auditory evoked potentials recording system mostly based on off-the-shelf electronics, in: XXVIII International Evoked Response Audiometry Study Group (IERASG-2023), pp. 83–84.
- [5] de la Torre, A., Valderrama, J.T., Segura, J.C., Alvarez, I.M., 2020. Latency dependent filtering and compact representation of the complete auditory pathway response. *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* 148, 599–613. doi:10.1121/10.0001673.
- [6] de la Torre, A., Valderrama, J.T., Segura, J.C., Alvarez, I.M., Garcia-Miranda, J., 2022. Subspace-constrained deconvolution of auditory evoked potentials. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* 151, 3745–3757. doi:10.1121/10.0011423.

©IWSSPA